

EFFECTS OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM ON THE LEARNING OUTCOMES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN INDONESIA: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Improving the quality of learning is pursued continuously, among others, through learning models. This study aims to investigate the impact of flipped classroom on learning outcomes in the domain of cognitive, affective and learning activities developed in elementary schools. This research is a literature study research, which analyzes the findings of previous research published in 2020-2023 in reputable national journals. Research findings show that flipped classroom improve critical and creative thinking, comprehension and learning outcomes in all subjects. In addition, flipped classroom increase student motivation, and self-regulated learning. The study concludes that a flipped classroom has a positive impact on students' mathematical understanding, understanding of science concepts, critical thinking, and learning outcomes. Also, a flipped classroom can increase student activeness, motivation, creativity, and self-regulated learning.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom; Learning Outcomes; Elementary School Students.

INTRODUCTION

Education in the 21st Century focuses on students' high-level thinking skills, ability to collaborate, and skill in using technological literacy. In addition, the digital era also triggers global competition. Teachers are required to move quickly and be innovative in carrying out their profession. In carrying out their duties as teachers and educators, teachers must determine teaching methods appropriate to students' learning outcomes, and choose effective learning media or teaching aids to meet learning objectives.

Because of rapid computer technology developments, there are many learning media based on ICT created such as learning videos, websites, documents, etc. The media can be delivered to students via the internet like LMS, websites, YouTube, blogs, emails, or social media like WhatsApp, Instagram, etc. One of the learning methods that utilizes educational technology is the Flipped Classroom. The learning process generally begins in the classroom. The teacher introduces the new concepts and explains them to the students in the classroom. At the end of the lesson, the teacher asks them to do homework individually or in groups. However, there is a learning model that is conducted oppositely, called the flipped classroom.

Students learn the content at home by themselves and teachers clarify students' understanding and continue through group discussion or problem-solving activities in the classroom (Fernández-Martín et al., 2020). Problem-solving activities in the classroom are the advantage of a flipped classroom because students can discuss with friends or ask the teacher when they need. Flipped Classroom reduces teacher dominance in direct learning so that student

involvement and interaction between students increases (Jamaluddin et al., 2022). Flipped classroom develops students' self-regulated learning, responsibility, and collaboration compared to the lectured-based approach (Al-Samarraie & Saeed, 2018)

According to (Ayob et al., 2020), the flipped classroom has the following characteristics: 1) change from knowledge acquisition activities in class to discussion and application of knowledge; 2) Students study the subject matter before face-to-face; 3) Students can interact online. The flipped classroom has four principles: 1) flexible learning environment, flipped learning can be modified by other methods because students have studied independently at home before; 2) change in learning culture from teacher-based to student-based; 3) the teaching material has been prepared by the teacher well; 4) Teachers remain professional in considering the material, methods, and assessment of lessons (Demirel, 2016).

Research on flipped classroom has largely focused on secondary and higher education levels, showing promising results in terms of increased student engagement, improved academic performance, and improved thinking skills. However, little is known about how this model can be effectively applied and adapted to fit the unique needs and developmental characteristics of primary school students. This study aimed to address this research gap by investigating flipped classrooms' impact on elementary school student's academic achievement, motivation, and attitudes. By examining the implementation of the flipped classroom model in the context of basic education, this study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on innovative teaching methodologies. The findings will provide insight into the feasibility of adopting a flipped classroom approach in an elementary school setting and offer practical recommendations for educators and policymakers interested in leveraging technology to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

METHOD

This is a literature study based on articles related to the research focus. This study investigates the impacts of flipped classroom in primary schools. Articles included have the following criteria: 1) The articles published in 2018-2023; 2) The research conducted in Indonesia; 3) The study conducted in elementary school students, and 4) Articles published in Indonesian journals index reputation.

Systematic searches are conducted using Publish or Perish. Search terms and keywords are used separately. The article was searched using Google Classroom using the keywords: 1) "flipped classroom" AND "primary school"; 2) "flipped classroom" AND "elementary school"; 3) "flipped learning" AND "primary school"; 4) "flipped learning" AND "elementary school". There were 962 articles found related to the flipped classroom. The articles were filtered based on journal index, articles in common, and completeness of the article's data. Finally, we got 23 articles that were eligible for analysis (Figure 1). Data analysis begins with data extraction. The data is concise and summarizes independently the data from the included studies. The data organized in Table 1, contain author ID, treatment, learning media, subject, and findings (Al-Samarraie & Hurmuzan, 2018).

Figure 1: Flowchart Article Screening

Table 1, shows that flipped classroom is most applied to science (11 articles) followed consecutively by mathematics (6 articles), and thematics (3articles). Meanwhile Islamic religious education, civic education, and social studies, one article. However, there is no article about the implementation of flipped classroom in Indonesian languages appropriate to the article's criteria.

RESULTS

The implementation of the flipped classroom in mathematics has a positive impact on mathematics understanding (Imawati et al., 2022) after watching the video, students were able to answer the questions correctly. Similar to the implementation of flipped classroom in science, flipped classroom improve students understanding (Savitri & Meilana, 2022).

Table 1: Articles Analyzed in the Study

Author ID	Treatment	Learning Media	Subject	Findings
(Latifah & Handayani, 2021)	FC	Video	Science	FC Positive influence on critical thinking skills
Agustin & Rindaningsih (2022)	FC-based realistic mathematics	Video	Mathematics	There is an influence of FC-based realistic mathematics on interest
Atmaja et al. (2021)	FC+ Geogebra	Video	Mathematics	Improve learning outcomes
(Chrismawati et al., 2021)	FC	PPT and Audio Visual	Science	FC can improve learning outcomes.
(Destriani & Warsah, 2022)	FC	video	Islamic Religious Education	Mengaktifkan siswa
(Fatmawati et al., 2021)	FC	Video	Civic Education	Increased creativity and learning outcomes
(Imawati et al., 2022)	FC	Video	Mathematics	Influence on the ability to understand mathematical concepts
(Isnainita et al., 2021)	FC	Text book	Thematic	improve learning outcomes
(Kurnianto et al., 2019)	FC	Video	Science	Improve critical thinking
(Kurnianto et al., 2019)	FC	Video	Science	Improve learning outcomes
(Hidayah & Mustadi, 2021)	FC	Video	Mathematics	FC Positive influence on learning outcomes
(Mulyanti et al., 2023)	FC modification peer instruction	Video	Science	There is an influence on learning outcomes
(Mulyanti et al., 2023)	FC based gamification	Video	Science	improved science learning outcomes
(Sholikhah & Alyani, 2022)	FC assisted by google slides	google slides	science	Influence on science learning outcomes
(Padmawati et al., 2022)	Blended Learning FC	PPT dan Video	Thematic	Successfully increase student learning independence.
(Sugiharti et al., 2022)	FC and Discovery Models	video	science	Influence on learning outcomes
(Saputro & Rusnilawati, 2023)	FC and Google Classroom	Google Classroom	Social Studies	Improve learning outcomes and Encrease self-regulation
(Savitri & Meilana, 2022)	FC	Video	Science	improve understanding of science concepts
(Suci et al., 2023)	FC	Video	Mathematics	Improve learning outcomes
(Trisnawati et al., 2021)	FC	Video	Science	Improve student activeness and learning outcomes
(Utamingtyas, 2022)	FC	Video	Thematic	There is an influence on learning motivation
(Sari & Wulandari, 2022)	FC	Video	Science	There is a significant influence on science learning outcomes
(Widodo et al., 2021)	FC	Video	Mathematics	Increased student independence

DISCUSSION

Flipped classroom increase student understanding of mathematics and science because students are actively involved in group discussions and collaborate to find solutions. The students share ideas and contribute to the group because they already have initial knowledge so they are confident exchanging opinions.

The flipped classroom also develops critical thinking skills in science (Kurnianto et al., 2019). Kurnianto explained that critical thinking skills are formed due to scaffolding, social interaction, and activities based on understanding. Likewise, Latifah and Handayani (2021) found a positive influence of the flipped classroom learning model on students' critical thinking skills. The improvement of students' critical thinking skills increases because students carry out activities, they can go through the exploration of various learning resources such as videos, powerpoints, e-books, and scientific articles. In class, students follow the learning process to deepen their understanding of the material through discussion and problem-solving to improve critical thinking skills.

A flipped classroom also improves students' creative thinking skills. Fatmawati et al. (2021) apply flipped classroom in social studies and conclude that flipped classroom improves students' creative thinking skills. Through group activities when face-to-face, students can discuss and find solutions for social problems as an implementation of the content.

Related to the influence of flipped classroom on learning outcomes, it was found that flipped classroom affected students' performance in geometry (Atmaja et al., 2021). Students learn at home through videos and during the implementation in class, students actively learn and seem enthusiastic and happy to learn mathematics. Suci et al. (2023) implementing video-assisted flipped classroom improves learning outcomes of classroom building properties of 3rd-grade students. Increasing student ability occurs with interactive learning, where students learn through visual manipulatives.

Meanwhile, the influence of flipped classroom on social studies was studied by one researcher and the research findings were that flipped classroom affected the ability to solve social studies problems (Saputro & Rusnilawati, 2023). Students can solve social studies problems with confidence after they study the learning videos that the teacher has given them before for them to study at home.

In addition, flipped classroom improves students' learning outcomes in science (Chrismawati et al., 2021). PowerPoint learning media in the flipped classroom model is also very helpful for teachers to deliver learning material easily and can be well received by students, to improve their learning outcomes. This finding is relevant to, the peer instruction type flipped classroom model can make students more active in learning, students have time to learn or understand learning material, and can improve learning outcomes in science (Melati & Santi, 2021). Likewise, gamification-based flipped classroom can increase student motivation and ultimately have a positive effect on science learning outcomes (Mulyanti et al., 2023).

Sari & Wulandari (2022) implementing video-assisted flipped classroom learning makes students understand the material easily and students' knowledge is strengthened by group discussions in class. Likewise, Sholikhah & Alyani (2022) found that student learning outcomes using the flipped classroom model were superior to the expository method. The advantage of the flipped classroom learning model is that students can learn independently, watch videos created by the teacher, and understand what they learn in class. Sugiharti et al. (2022) found flipped classroom combined with discovery learning models improve student learning outcomes in science for human respiratory organs because students are more ready to accept learning, and can understand their concepts to train students to be creative and think critically.

The role of the flipped classroom in developing civic education learning outcomes is examined by (Fatmawati et al., 2021) that the information technology-based flipped classroom is more influential in improving student learning outcomes on the material diversity of individual characteristics of PPKn lesson content. Students are first given online learning content can be in the form of videos or other online learning content for them to learn homework is done in class with the teacher and Students discuss and solve questions or problems.

In thematic learning, FC improves student learning outcomes because learning is interesting and fun for students (Isnainita et al., 2021). Inline to Pujilestari et al. (2022) concluded that a flipped classroom learning model assisted by the use of video media can improve student thematic learning outcomes.

Based on the findings of the research above, it is known that flipped classroom improve student learning outcomes in all subjects, including positively affecting understanding, critical thinking skills, and creative thinking. The improvement in learning outcomes and thinking skills is caused by students having studied the material independently and the opportunity to apply knowledge to solve problems during face to face in classrooms with other students (Cho et al., 2021). Knowledge acquisition before face-to-face makes students better prepared from the cognitive aspect to have direct discussions (Papadakis et al., 2017). Besides, students collaborate in the implementation of knowledge in during the classroom phase (Ayob et al., 2020). Discussion is one way for students to sharpen and clarify knowledge obtained independently in the before-class phase. Also, when students discuss to solve problems, students' critical thinking, creative thinking and understanding develop so that improve student learning outcomes.

Based on the affective aspect, it was found that flipped classroom can increase student activeness. Destriani & Warsah (2022) found flipped classroom increases student engagement. Students become more active in class. The flipped classroom learning model can increase student motivation and interest, provide more real learning experiences, and learning outcomes, and encourage student learning activities both inside and outside the classroom. The influence of flipped classroom on student activeness is also concluded by Trisnawati et al. (2021), that students conduct experiments on their own, discuss, and are able to solve problems. Moreover, flipped classroom also increases motivation. Studies conducted by Utamingtyas and Evitasari (2022) found that students are more motivated in learning and more flexible in learning

learning materials independently. In virtual face-to-face, teachers and students have discussions to discuss learning material more deeply. In addition to motivation, flipped classroom positively affects students' interest in learning. Agustin & Rindaningsih (2022) examines the application of flipped classroom-based realistic mathematics. They found realistic math learning based on flipped classroom that can increase students' interest in learning. Flipped classroom provides opportunities for students to explore learning tools, and share ideas with peers. Student activities in the classroom become effective because students have previously learned the material through videos sent through WhatsApp to their parents.

Furthermore, flipped classroom affects students' self-regulated learning. Flipped classroom makes learning more interesting with the support of various platforms so that students are more active and student independence increases (Padmawati et al., 2022). Likewise, Saputro and Rusnilawati (2023) concluded that there was an increase in self-regulated learning after implementing flipped classroom with by Google Classroom. Students are interested in observing videos created by the teacher and they can repeat the videos if they need. This activity fosters student independence in learning. The findings were similar to Widodo et al. (2021) that videos were very helpful for students and raised their curiosity.

In addition to improving cognition, flipped classroom also improve students' affective domains including motivation, self-regulated learning and curiosity. The increase in learning motivation is triggered by students being able to learn according to their needs at home and the teaching materials provided by the teacher are interesting for students (Havwini & Wu, 2019). Furthermore, students who already have an understanding can be more confident when expressing their knowledge in class. The feedback and appreciation given by teachers increase student confidence (Jdaitawi, 2019).

Flipped classroom consists of three phases, before class, during class and after class. In before learning in class phase, students learn teaching materials with various media. The most media used are video (18 studies), Power Point (2 studies), teaching materials (1 study), and Google Slides (1 study). The platforms used are WhatsApp (18 studies), Google Classroom (2 studies). In addition, the application used is geogebra (1 study). Increased student learning participation, mainly because it is supported by the use of collaborative technology such as Google Docs, Google Classroom, and Edmodo (Bond, 2020). During class phase, some researchers modify flipped classroom with learning methods. These include modifying flipped classroom with realistic mathematical education (Latifah & Handayani, 2021), discovery learning (Sholikhah & Alyani, 2022; Sugiharti et al., 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of flipped classroom can be distinguished from cognitive and affective aspects. Based on cognitive aspects, flipped classroom can improve mathematical understanding, understanding of science concepts, critical thinking. Besides, flipped classroom improve students learning outcomes in social studies, science, and civic education. Based on the affective aspect, it was found that flipped classroom can increase student activeness, motivation, creativity, and self-regulated learning.

Flipped classroom engage students in before-class activities and during-class activities. Activities before learning in class are dominated by watching video activities, while the rest is carried out in the form of reading textbooks, PowerPoint, audiovisual, Google Slides, and Google Classroom. Face-to-face learning activities are carried out in the form of discussions, problem-solving, exercises, questions and answers, and individual assignments. The learning methods combined with flipped classroom are discovery, gamification, interactive media, role-playing, and RME

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